

Development of legal education in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

Islamic Sharia forms the basis of laws in the KSA and was first formulated in 1932. The Islamic provisions are considered as supreme over the codified laws and direct the state's regulations. A close review of the Saudi legal system makes it apparent that it follows both the written and the unwritten laws. Because the Shari'ah is considered as the state's supreme law and cannot be overridden by the codified laws. This study has taken into account the given principle and make recommendations as for how the curriculum can redesign to improve the capabilities of prospective professionals regarding integrating the different law components with the fundamentals of Sharia law. The study examines degree plans in the KSA universities; most of these offer mandatory Islamic law courses. The adequacy of these courses, however, remains questionable as for whether these apply to the comprehensive provisions of Islamic law or not. Results suggest that courses must be offered that allow the students to not only develop stronger foundations in general but also enable them better integrate the non-codified rules of law with the Islamic law.

Keywords: Law development, legal education, sharia, Saudi Arabia, KSA

1. INTRODUCTION

Saudi Arabia has seen a tremendous increase in legal education. This change has especially occurred as a result of recent developments in the legal system of the Kingdom. The recent developments include codification of various rules in the Kingdom. The law in Saudi Arabia can primarily be described as consolidation of both the written and unwritten laws. State's laws, regulations, and the decisions taken in courts are grounded in the fundamentals of Shari'ah. However, the kingdom also follows the modern system of codification of rules and laws. Since codification has only recently been gained widespread recognition among the authorities, this has raised an urgent need of legal professionals who can employ their skills to pace-up the process. Expansion in the scope of legal codification has encouraged different Arabian universities to offer courses in the respective realm and therefore have introduced

bachelor degrees. Notwithstanding, the international advancement and expansion of legal education pose significant challenges to the KSA which is why the legal education cannot be embraced the way it is required. This has significantly halted the progress and made it difficult to pursue the change. This emphasizes the need of conducting empirical researches to direct the development of legal education in KSA likely the way it has successfully emerged in other countries.

1.1 Literature Review

This research aims to appraise the development procedures followed in KSA for legal education and ways how the supremacy of sharia law can better be integrated to influence the law in general. There have been some studies conducted that provide insights to the development of legal education in the UK; however, only a few of these have taken into account the effect of sharia law.

Working paper presented in 2011 at the Prince Sultan University highlights the need of revising the legal education paradigms in the KSA [1]. Dr. Ayoub Alga bough presented this paper and highlighted that the system of legal education must be structured in KSA through improving the level of sharia law knowledge by the law graduates. The solution that the author has proposed for this change is to extend the duration of the degree and introduction of a foundation year (i.e., a five years bachelor degree). This will allow the undergraduates gain sufficient knowledge and would be able to understand its validity against different decisions and regulation the state issues at different instances. The graduates would consequently be able to work in all the fields of legal practice including the judiciary. Moreover, the universities will be able to offer effective courses for Islamic law.

Rayan Alkhalwai presented some significant insights to the legal education in Saudi Arabia. The study critically analyzed the efficacy of current plan the Taibah University applies to the graduates and the opportunities available to the legal market [2]. Data was collected based on curriculum review; the study examined its comprehensiveness and adequacy to meet the advanced

standards of legal education. The study identifies the current curriculum as inappropriate regarding the admission and selection criteria followed, the background of professors, and the overall environment. The author concludes that the current curriculum does not allow graduates to gain success with the prospective legal frameworks. The curriculum must be revised since it does not follow the realistic market perspectives applied in the KSA. Professors responsible for rendering knowledge are hired from different backgrounds, and the assessments they undergo are only weaker. The study identified a significant lack of qualifications among the high school students joining the Taibah University for further law studies.

Development of legal education constitutes a sensitive issue because of modernization of laws is considered as abandonment or drift to the Islamic laws. This remains the particular reason why the matter is only sparsely documented and acquires lesser support regarding modernization of laws and legal studies [3]. The issue is mostly documented on websites, the social media platform, and newspaper websites. Proponents of the legal education development and advancement often are criticized for their beliefs; they are accused of not believing in the power of sharia law [4] [5].

1.2 Research Problems

The research aims to analyze the significance of the law in the KSA and how it embraces the knowledge of sharia law. Law students often face confusion regarding the Islamic provisions and how the newly codified laws complement them. Moreover, how future judges may obtain a certificate in sharia law and how the degree in law or sharia may help the prospective lawyers.

1.3 Research Questions

The research mainly aims to address the critical challenges that hinder the development of legal education in Saudi Arabia.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research will follow an analytical design of legal education through examining the various, codes, laws, and constitutions in the KSA. The research will also assess the curricular and degree plans that various law institutions in the KSA employ.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

Below are provided the different objectives that the study underpins

- Analysis of the legal systems in the KSA
- Analysis of the judicial systems in the KSA
- Analysis of the legal practice in KSA

- Analysis of the structure of the legal education in KSA
- Assessment of the curricular and degree plans that different legal institutions follow
- Repercussions of a fragmented legal education system

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Legal System in the KSA

History of the KSA's legal system can be traced back to 1932 when its constitution was introduced. Ever since it was formed, the Islamic law reins the state's regulations across the KSA. This principle was further validated in 1992 when the Basic Law of Governance was introduced [6]. Article 7 of the given governance law provides that the KSA draws its governance from the Holy Book (Quran) and Sunnah; both of these forms the guiding sources of the law in the KSA [7].

The article 46 further provides that the judiciary must act as an independent authority and there shall be no power exercised over judicial functioning, but only the power in the Islamic sharia. Furthermore, the article 48 provides that the Islamic sharia principles must be applied to all the cases in the courts in the way specified in Quran and Sunnah and also the ruler led laws conforming the Quran and Sunnah.

The article 67 finally states that the regulatory authority may exercise no power in the promulgation of rules and laws that encourage the realization of the common good and prevent the state from harms. This prevention must be guided by the sharia principles [7] [8] [9]. The Royal Decree established Shura Council in 1992 which validates the similar principle. Article 2 of the Council applies that the council strictly adheres to the sources of Islamic legislation and that all members of the council must make deliberate efforts to bring the best in public interest and strengthen the bonds of unity among communities across the nation [10].

3.2 Sources of Legislation in the Saudi Legal System

As mentioned previously, the article 48 emphasizes courts to apply Islamic provisions to all the case hearings, in a way the Quran and Sunnah indicates, and the rules of law issued by the ruler of the state that conforms to the Quran and Sunnah. Provisions in the given article are critical to understanding since the principle is vulnerable to create an enigma [11]. This does not clarify if the judges can apply the written laws to cases or must only stick to the sharia laws while ignoring modern rules; the discretion, at this moment, is significantly vague.

This can better be understood by considering the example of the commercial law which undoubtedly forms the oldest written law in the KSA. The Commercial Courts first

disseminated the law in 1970. It is important to note that majority of judges refuse to apply positive laws mainly due to the belief that such laws are not sharia led but are man-made and that application of such laws would breach the sharia [12][13]. As a result, the state has established quasi-judicial committees which are highly administrative. The purpose of these committees is to adjudicate the financial and the commercial matters [11] [14].

These committees are increasingly important since they support dispute resolution processes through employing a competent and specialized team of members. Furthermore, they help solve the issues that arise as a result of judiciary's failure/refusal to apply the codified laws because of fear of abandonment of the customary sharia provisions [14].

The different codified laws followed in the KSA include the Labor Law 2004, the Judicial Code of 2006, the court proceedings of 2014, and the 2014 criminal procedures. However, it is important to note that none of these laws follow the legislative sources. Labor Law has been identified as an exception. The article 223 of the law applies that 'none of the organs of these institutions have the power to issue any codes claiming that there is a lack of procedure or law and must draw upon the principles of Islamic law and rely either on case law, custom or the rules of justice' [11].

The article, nevertheless, fails to establish that what hierarchy of sources must be followed and therefore allows the judiciary to follow a discretion as they deem as appropriate. Minister of Labor formed a body specifically dedicated to handling the labor disputes. This body is responsible for adjudication instead of leaving the labor matters at the expense of the regular courts [15].

These findings relative to the Shari'ah law application over the regulations of states applies that the prospective legal professionals must be provided with adequate knowledge of legislation, so they are not only able to understand the Shari'ah laws and the codified positive laws, but may also retain a right complementary balance to make informed decision making where and when necessary.

3.3 The judicial system in KSA

The reform of the judicial system in KSA was considered through the new judiciary system that was developed in 2007 and replaced the old judiciary system of 1975. The development of two-tier litigation system was one of the notable advancement. The adequate implantation of the law was ensured by the Supreme Court of justice that refers to the evolution by another process. Secondly, the article 9 about the development of competent courts consists the following;

1. The Supreme Court
2. Courts of appeals

3. First instance courts, which are:
 - a. General courts
 - b. Penal courts
 - c. Family courts
 - d. Commercial courts
 - e. Labor courts

By this law, the above mentioned have the jurisdiction over matters that is the procedure of law before the courts of sharia and the law of criminal procedures.

Upon the approval of the king, the council of the supreme judicial council may establish other specialized courts.

Qualification of Judges (conditioned by a degree in Sharia Law). The candidate shall fulfill the following requirements for appointing as a judge;

- (a) Saudi nationality by descent is required.
- (b) Must have the good characters and conduct.
- (c) He shall be fully competent to hold the position of a judge by Sharia.
- (d) The degree of tip Sharia colleges in the Kingdom is required or any other degree that certifies the passing of the examination that is prepared by the Supreme Judicial Council.
- (e) The age of the candidate must be above forty for the appointment of an appeals judge and above twenty-two for other ranks in the judiciary.
- (f) The candidate must not be convicted to the impinging of religious crime or honor. The candidate should not be involved in the subject of disciplinary action that dismissed the candidate from public office, even for re-habitation.

The above-mentioned paragraphs of this article discuss the qualities for becoming the judge of Sharia law or equivalent.

However, not all laws are codified as mentioned in this paper earlier and the highest source of law in KSA is the Sharia Law. There is an example of Civil Code and the Penal Code which are not codified and rely on the provisions of Islamic law, but the Code of Civil Procedure and the Code of Criminal procedure have the large importance of procedural laws according to the legal system. The weaknesses of the application of the law are the legal qualification of a judge in Sharia and their non-familiarity with the procedural laws. However, these laws are also not properly applied in many cases by the judiciary of Saudi due to the lack of expertise of judges in the procedural laws.

3.4 The Legal Profession in KSA

Law forms a profession that is still in the developmental phase in Saudi Arabia and does not impact the practices of courts. Procedures for lawyers in the KSA were first issued

in 2001 [2]. Alkhalawi [2] and Karl [11] provide insights to the different conditions that must necessarily be followed for practicing law in the KSA. The most prominent requirement for this is the bachelor's degree. It forms a sensible assumption that lawyers with only sharia comprehensions show limited understandings for the modern laws. This weakens the overall structure of law in the KSA.

3.5 Teaching Law in KSA

The first law department in Saudi Arabia was established in 1980 at the Kind Saud University and was named as the Regulations Department. This department was formed as part of the Faculty of Administrative Sciences. The department, however, was transformed to an independent college of law and political science in 2006 [16]. It started offering bachelor's degree in law for both the boys and girls. Another Regulation Department was later established at the King Abdul Aziz University in 1987 as part of the Faculty of Management and Economics. This department offered bachelors in law degree as well. Similar to the former one, this department was also transformed to an independent college in 2012 and was specifically named as the Faculty of law [17].

The past ten years have seen a tremendous increase in Saudi universities with law faculties. There have been 27 public universities located in different regions in the KSA. In addition to these, ten private universities have also been formed that offer law undergraduate programs. Law courses are also offered in some universities under the title of 'College of Sharia' and the Faculty of Business. It is important to note that it is only recently that the name of 'Faculty of Law' has been given to these departments since the majority of these are still acknowledged as Department of Regulations. This assumption is based on the fact that inclusion of term 'law' indicates for the human-made laws that sometimes are contrary to the sharia provisions [2]. Despite the fact that female lawyers are only rarely accepted in the Saudi Courts; the law education is available for both the men and women.

3.6 Degree Plans of Law Programs in KSA

The foundations of legal education in Saudi Arabia are entrenched in Jordan, Egypt, and France. Majority of the degree programs offered in KSA are similar to these countries based on duration, credit hours, and the nature of courses offered. Moreover, the sharia courses offered aside from the other law courses vary based on the department/college, but must not exceed a total 15% [2]. For instance, the fundamental courses of law taught in different departments include shari'ah policies, the family law, and principles of jurisprudence, rules, and inheritance, rules of jurisprudence, shari'ah policies, and zakat. An

overview of the law programs offered in KSA makes apparent some challenges. The problem can be found in the criminal law and civil law courses. As mentioned previously, The KSA does not codify these laws; therefore the sharia is followed. Contrastingly, the law colleges also follow certain courses from the other countries that are heavily influenced by the Latin Legal System; for instance, Egypt and Jordan. Another challenge that can be highlighted from these findings is the appearance of non-Arab nationalities as teachers in KSA who have actually got their law degrees in other jurisdictions and does not solely adhere to the Islamic laws. This significantly impacts the understanding and comprehension of sharia law among students [2].

4. CONCLUSION

Findings of the research suggests that the integral problem that the KSA encounters relative to the legal studies is uniqueness of the Islamic system. Despite it has a codified system of regulations, the sharia is still considered as supreme. This has led to significant confusion in the Saudi system of education. It can be construed from the findings that comprehensive reforms to the legal system, the judicial system, and the legal structure are inevitable to develop the KSA's legal education. In order to resolve these challenges, the researcher makes following recommendations

- Legal provisions must be made explicit and clear so that they can be enforced to the written laws resulting in no violation of the Islamic provisions. The element of judges' discretion must be removed; they must not be allowed to decide between application of the sharia and the written laws.
- Reforms should be made to the KSA's judicial system. This can be supported based on the fact that the system was last updated ten years ago and the new judicial system has not yet fully implemented particularly in regards to development of the specialized courts.
- Specialized courts' judges must hold more than certificates i.e. certificates of both the sharia and the modern law to make the process more fluent and adequate.
- Regimens of legal practicing must be revised so that only the holders of legal certificates are able to enter the profession of law. A strengthened merit is created so that only the competent individuals are able to practice law. Individuals holding certificates in law must show sufficient familiarity with the sharia provisions. Contrarily, holders of the shari'ah law must show adequate knowledge of the legal subjects

essentially required to direct the criminal and civil law proceedings.

- Educational curricula must be development based on the global development and to meet the requirements of both the local and the international community.
- Teachers must not stick to the traditional shari'ah, but this must be taught in light of the recent developments.

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